

PROGRESSIV SHTAMPLASH KONSTRUKSIYALARINI REJALASHTIRISH. PLANNING OF PROGRESSIVE STAMPING CONSTRUCTIONS

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Nosimmetrik progressiv shtamlash, shtamp ko'prigini rejalashtirish

ANNOTATSIYA

Murakkab presslashni talab qiladigan shtamplangan qismlarni ommaviy ishlab chiqarish uchun doimo progressiv shtamlar to'plamidan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Agar shtamplangan qismlarni chuqur olish kerak bo'lsa, ayniqsa assimetrik bo'lsa, progressiv qoliplar to'plamini tanlash qiyin. Asimetrik chuqur chizilgan qismlar keyingi bosqichga o'tish paytida og'irlik ta'siriga juda sezgir bo'lgani uchun ularni matrisoning yuzini yuqori aniqlikda aniqlash qiyin.

Recently, the adoption of high-strength steel plates has increased to reduce vehicle weight and improve collision safety performance [1], and body parts are also being changed to highly difficult shapes for reasons of simplification of parts [2]. Most automobile body and chassis parts are manufactured by thin plate press molding, but in the case of parts with a deep drawing depth and complex curved shape, it contains complex deformation conditions that combine various individual processes, so a high-level press forming method is required.

The progressive method is a technology that can combine various processes within a

single mold, and can realize unmanned operation through automation as well as reducing production time and increasing efficiency through mass production [3, 4]. However, the applied parts are simply symmetrical or limited to small parts, and high-level process design and mold making technology are required to secure stable quality for complex parts.

The car seat side cushion panel of Fig 1 supports the structure of the seat frame and is a major part that is repeatedly affected by the occupant's riding comfort and irregular behavior to be.

Fig. 1 3D model of seat side cushion panel

The automobile seat side cushion panel is molded from a thin plate of 0.8t, and has a drawing depth of 80 mm or more and a complex curved shape asymmetrically. Therefore, in order to apply the progressive method, it is necessary to solve the problems such as twisting, shaking, and jamming of the panel during the strip transport process due to the asymmetric shape and high height [5].

In this study, in order to apply the progressive method of automobile seat side cushion panel products, which are body parts with asymmetric deep-drawing complex curved shapes, the product was formed by preventing the product from shaking up and down when attaching and detaching the product during the strip transfer process between each process. We would like to present a design proposal for a strip bridge with better rigidity so that it can be accurately seated in the mold of the next process.

1. Drawing process molding analysis

For the bridge design for the progressive molding of the seat side cushion panel, which is an asymmetric deep-drawing product, a self-weight deflection analysis was performed after the drawing process forming analysis. When transferring the panels between processes, the strength for stabilizing the mold and maintaining the balance of the panel In order to derive a design for a reinforcing bridge, the amount of panel deformation after molding and self-weight deflection analysis was compared.

1.1 Forming analysis condition setting

For molding analysis, after one-step blanking, two-step drawing analysis was performed. Fig. 2 shows the analysis model of the panel and drawing process after the blanking process.

For the drawing process mold, the upper mold is the master, the panel material is SPRC440, the panel thickness is 0.8t, and the

molding type is drawing. The friction coefficient between the panel and the mold was 0.1, and the element was set to 1 mm from the initial size of 8 mm to the final 1 mm by applying the 4-step adaptive mesh [6].

In the forming order, the upper die comes down first to hold the holder, and the final product is formed by forming as much as 70 mm of punch stroke while maintaining the holding force of 3 tons.

2.2 Forming analysis result of drawing process

2.2.1 Initial Bridge Forming Analysis Results

Fig. 3 shows the molding process of the drawing process, and as a result of the molding analysis, the bridge part is molded and the flesh is insufficient

Fig. 2 Blanking shape and tool setting for stamping

Fig. 3 Drawing processes with initial bridge

The load could be checked, and as a result of the formability analysis through the Forming Limit Diagram (FLD), it was possible to predict that the burst would start 50 mm before the completion of forming. Therefore, the bridge was modified

and designed to secure the initial flesh and rigidity.

2.2.2 Design of the shape of the bridge for securing and reinforcing strength

To secure the flesh of the bridge part, Fig. As in Case 1 of 4, the bridge shape was modified and designed.

For comparison of deformation amount, molding analysis and self-weight deflection analysis were performed on the shapes of Cases 2 to 4, in which the front and rear bridges of Case 1 were separately arranged.

Fig. 4 Bridges for the comparison of panel deformation

Fig. 5 Drawing processes with the bridge of case 1

Fig. 6 Boundary conditions for gravity simulation

2.2.3 Drawing process forming analysis after bridge reinforcement

Fig. 1 shows the drawing process forming process for 4 is shown.

During the drawing process after reinforcing the bridge, there was no cracking of the panel on the molding limit diagram, and it was found that the shape of the bridge was twisted 40 mm before final molding.

2. Analysis of panel deformation through self-weight deflection analysis

After the drawing process, self-weight deflection analysis [7] for 4 bridge cases was performed to verify the shape of strips and bridges that can be balanced during the process of moving up and down, moving the panel, and forming the product in the progressive mold. did.

The boundary conditions for self-weight deflection analysis are shown in Fig. As shown in Fig. 6, both rotation (R: rotation) and transfer (T: translation) movements were fixed in the same way as the constraint conditions of the panel in the actual progressive process.

The results of the self-weight deflection analysis for the five bridge shape cases are shown in Fig. As shown in 7, in the progressive gradual forming process of a car seat side cushion panel with an asymmetric deep-drawing complex curved surface, when transferring, dismounting, and seating between processes, -2.93 to 2.89 mm in Case 1, -5.06 to 7.63 in Case 2 mm, Case 3 was 7.97~32.60mm, Case 4 was -9.60~15.30mm, and Case 5 was -12.87~56.30mm.

(a)Case 1

(b)Case 2

(c)Case 3

single tracked, single carried, v4

(d)Case 4

Fig. 7 Results of the deflection analysis by gravity in 4cases of belt bridge.

3. Conclusion

When press-molding asymmetric deep drawing products such as automobile seat cushion side panels by the progressive method, due to excessive inflow of panels due to deep drawing and an asymmetric

center of gravity, a typical strip bridge is used to remove the upper and lower parts of the product from the mold and provide stable separation. song is difficult In this study, a bridge with flesh reinforcement and strength reinforced on the existing bridge

was designed through the analysis of the drawing process.

- (1) As a result of drawing forming analysis, it was found that the existing strip bridge started to burst 50 mm before forming completion.
- (2) The modified strip bridge with flesh reinforcement and strength reinforcement did not burst during the drawing process analysis, and it was found that the twisting phenomenon occurred 40 mm before the completion of molding.
- (3) As a result of performing self-weight deflection analysis with the same boundary conditions as the constraint conditions in the progressive forming

process of the actual panel, the maximum deformation was 2.89 mm and the minimum -2.93 mm in Case 1 (a bridge shape that holds both left and right). In case 4 (a shape that holds only the left side in a plan view), the maximum deformation was 56.30 mm, and the minimum deformation was -12.87 mm.

Therefore, in the case of the seat side cushion panel, which is an asymmetric deep-drawing body part, it was confirmed that a strip bridge with a shape that holds both left and right sides when press-molding with the progressive method is most suitable.

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